

BANKO JANAKARI

बनको जानकारी

A JOURNAL OF FORESTRY INFORMATION FOR NEPAL

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Each volume will have four parts. The journal will generally be distributed free in Nepal to anyone professionally concerned with forestry. Exchange agreements will usually be welcome. Otherwise a charge of NR300, £10, or \$15 annually will be made (to include postage). Cheques should be made payable to 'FRP Publications'. Single copies of individual articles can be supplied free of charge.

Articles, short notes, news items, or letters to the Editor may be submitted to Banko Janakari in almost any form, provided they are legible. They are accepted on the understanding that the Editor may shorten or alter them in any way, but this will be done (especially in the case of scientific articles) in consultation with the author as far as possible, depending on the difficulties of communication.

It will generally be helpful, however, if authors use the articles in the current issue as a model, e.g. in giving the name of the organization they work for. For references it is even more important to give full information than to set them out in standard form.

If possible, illustrations should be at least 25 % larger than they are to appear in print. Photographs should be black and white and should be sent either as the negative (which will be returned) or as a glossy print. Tables should be kept to a reasonable width; if very wide ones are required it is best to discuss their format in advance.

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AFFORESTATION RESEARCH FIELD DAY IN THE BHABAR TERAI

A field day incorporating visits to the Adabhar trial site and the Hetauda research nursery will be held under the auspices of the Forestry Research Project on Thursday 26 March, based in Hetauda. An illustrated talk on bamboos will be presented in Hetauda the previous evening. Further details fom:

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FOREST MANAGEMENT WORKSHOP

The Nepal-Australia Forestry Project has taken the initiative in planning a Forest Management Workshop 'immediately after Tihar' (November 1987). A committee has been established, consisting of Sharad Karmacharya (CFDP), M.D. Rajbhandari (Department of Forest), Nick Roche (IHDP) and Gary King (NAFP), and discussions are going on with other interested organizations about the agenda. Contact:

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